

New Phytologist Supporting Information

Article title: **Long-term high temperatures affect seed maturation and seed coat integrity in *Brassica napus***

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The following Supporting Information is available for this article:

Fig. S1 Representative picture of the silique culture system for ABA treatment.

Fig. S2 Profiles of auxin and its metabolites in *Brassica napus* Topas seeds, isolated embryos and seed coats.

Fig. S3 Representative pictures of the seeds and embryos measured in Fig. 3.

Fig. S4 Venn diagrams summarising the transcriptional response of Topas seeds at HT.

Fig. S5 GO terms associated with the transcriptional response of Topas seeds to HT.

Fig. S6 Expression clusters of the transcriptional response of the Topas seeds to HT.

Table S1 Full dataset for the DEGs for all the comparisons.

Table S2 DEGs for dormancy, ABA and pectin metabolism related.

Table S3 Misregulated GO terms associated with plant cell wall, hormone, cell cycle, metabolic, heat response and developmental pathways.

Table S4 DEGs and GO terms associated with each of the clusters.

Method S1 Co-expression cluster mapping of genes.

Fig. S1 Representative picture of the silique culture system for ABA treatment. Siliques of 14 DAP from HT and 18 DAP from CT were collected, surface-sterilised and cultivated on $\frac{1}{2}$ MS with 0.8% plant agar, 0.05% plant preservative for tissue culture media, supplemented with 10 μ M ABA or the same volume of DMSO as negative control. The tubes were incubated in the greenhouse with the plants under the same growth conditions. Seeds were collected and scored at maturity.

Fig. S2 Profiles of auxin and its metabolites in *Brassica napus* Topas seeds, isolated embryos and seed coats. Samples are Topas seeds from 14 DAP to 36 DAP from CT (blue), HT (red, dark red). From 20 DAP, HT seeds were separated into intact seeds (red) and SCR seeds (dark red). IAA and metabolites were also profiled from embryos and seed coats from 14 DAP and 18 DAP seeds. Quantification is presented as pmol per g fresh weight. Measurements were performed for indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), anthranilate (ANT), tryptophan (TRP), indole-3-pyruvic acid (IPyA), 2-oxoindole-3-acetic acid (oxIAA), and IAA-aspartate (IAA_{sp}). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences in HT and between 14 DAP HT and 18 DAP CT in a multiple t-test using the Holm-Sidak method (*, **, *** and **** correspond to values of $p > 0.05 > p > 0.01$, $0.01 > p > 0.001$, and $p < 0.001$, respectively). n.s., not significant.

Fig. S3 Representative pictures of the seeds and embryos measured in Fig. 3. Embryo and seed pictures of *Brassica napus* Westar and Topas seeds developed at CT and HT. Scale bars represent 2 mm.

Fig. S4 Venn diagrams summarising the transcriptional response of Topas seeds at HT. (a, b) Venn diagram showing the differentially transcribed genes (DEGs) unique to or shared between the 14 and 18 DAP seeds grown at CT and HT. Up DEGs (a) and down DEGs (b) are presented. (c, d) Venn diagram showing the differentially transcribed genes (DEGs) unique to or shared between the 20 DAP intact and SCR seeds grown at CT and HT. Up DEGs (c) and down DEGs (d) are presented. The number of DEGs shared between the age and growth temperature of the seeds is shown in the intersecting region of the Venn diagram. The full dataset is provided in Table S1.

Fig. S5 GO terms associated with the transcriptional response of Topas seeds to HT. Shown are GO terms related to cell cycle (a), hormonal regulation (b), heat stress (c), development (d), and changes in metabolic pathways (e). The full list and GO and associated transcripts are provided in Tables S1 and S3.

Fig. S6 Expression cluster of the transcriptional response of the Topas seeds to HT

Methods S1 Co-expression cluster mapping of genes.

Clustering analysis of the expression data was conducted using the Clust tool (v1.18.0) (Abu-Jamous & Kelly, 2018). The expression profile data values were normalised through the built-in methods of Clust (quantile, log2, and Z-score normalisation) (Andrews, 2010). The k-means clustering method was employed for the analysis, with a minimum of 20 clusters. The tightness weight and Q3 outlier threshold parameters were set to their default values.